

Is Cancer A Roll of the Genetic Dice? Implications for Clinical Trial Design and Personalized Cancer Therapy

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Our current paradigm supporting the genetic origins of cancer took center stage in the last decades of the twentieth century as important new research revealed the significance of mutated cellular oncogenes and tumor suppressor genes as primary causes of malignant transformation. These seminal research studies led to the unraveling of key cell cycle control pathways responsible for malignant transformation and progression that, not only provided a theoretical rationale for the use of traditional chemotherapy drugs such as methotrexate and paclitaxel that block cell cycle progression, but also laid the groundwork for a new era of cancer medicine based on the development of monoclonal antibodies and small molecule therapeutics designed to block the activities of runaway genes responsible for the vast majority of human cancers.

Ever since the identification of the so-called “Philadelphia” chromosome as a ubiquitous genetic fingerprint for chronic myeloid leukemia (CML) by Hungerford and Nowell in 1960 (see Figure 1), the identification of specific genes responsible for human cancers has been a primary research goal. Even more spectacularly, the discovery of imatinibmesylate (also known as Gleevec) an inhibitor of the oncogenic *abl* gene activated by reciprocal transformation in CML, showed that gene targeted anti-cancer drugs can have a dramatic and profound therapeutic efficacy in patients with CML or gastrointestinal stromal tumors (GIST) whose cancers contain this mutation.

Figure 1 The “Philadelphia” chromosome resulting from chromosome 9:22 reciprocal translocation was the first reproducible genetic abnormality to be linked to the origins of a specific human cancer, chronic myeloid leukemia (CML). The oncogenically activated *abl* gene is the target of imatinib mesylate, used successfully in the treatment of patients with this type of cancer.

The Gleevec success story opened the door to the era of personalized cancer medicine that is based on the concept that the identification of specific genetic lesions in individual patient tumors will facilitate the appropriate use of gene-targeted drugs tailored to eradicate a malignancy based on its assessed genetic profile.

This gene –targeted therapeutic approach led to the FDA approval of trastuzumab (Herceptin), a targeted monoclonal antibody, as a treatment for patients with breast cancer who test positive for its genetic target, the amplified HER2/neu oncogene. Likewise, gene-targeted therapeutics cetuximab and panitumumab were approved for use in patients with colon cancer containing the oncogenic ras mutation (see Table 1).

List of Cancer Treatment-Related Companion Diagnostics				
CDx			Drug	Indication
Biomarker	Type	Year CDx approval		
KRAS Mutation	LDT	2006	Cetuximab, Panitumumab	Colorectal Cancer
	PMA	2012		
BRAF V600E Mutation	PMA	2011	Vemurafenib	Melanoma
ALK Fusion	PMA	2011	Crizotinib	NSCLC
EGFR Mutation	LDT	2003	Gefitinib, Erlotinib	NSCLC
HER2 Amplification	PMA	1998	Trastuzumab	Breast Cancer
	PMA	2008		
BCR-ABL Translocation	PMA	2005	Imatinib,	CML
			Dasatinib,	
			Nilotinib	

Table 1 CML: Chronic Myeloid Leukemia; LDT: Laboratory Developed Test in CLIA certified clinical laboratory; NSCLC: Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer; PMA: Pre-Market Approval by the FDA Source: Barnett et al, Clin Chem 2013;59:198–201.[3]

Promising small scale clinical trial data supporting the use of genetic medicines in patients whose tumors test positive for the specific mutations targeted by these drugs have provided additional impetus to the rapidly developing field of personalized cancer treatment based on a reading of the abnormal genetic code responsible for malignant transformation (see Figure 2).

However, the story of personalized gene-targeted cancer medicine does not end here. Recently published clinical trial results of a high profile molecularly targeted drug have failed to live up to the high expectations engendered by the success of Gleevec. At the 2013 annual American Society for Clinical Oncology (ASCO) conference, Mark Gilbert, professor of neuro-

oncology at the MD Anderson Cancer Center, presented the disappointing results of a well-crafted phase III Radiation Therapy Oncology Group (RTOG) study of the effects of the angiogenesis inhibitor, bevacizumab (Avastin), that showed no clinical difference from a placebo in the treatment of patients newly diagnosed with an aggressive form of brain cancer, glioblastoma multiforme (GBM). Not only did this disappointing clinical outcome raise questions about the potential efficacy of targeted therapeutics, but it also called into question the relevance and correlation between this large scale randomized clinical trial and earlier smaller scale studies that showed statistically significant evidence of tumor shrinkage and a several month delay to disease progression in the study arm enrolling patients treated with Avastin. This positive clinical benefit was not upheld by the larger more comprehensive study. From an economic standpoint, the unsatisfactory results follow \$6 billion in worldwide sales over the duration of a 16 year of clinical trial study that ultimately indicated no clinical benefit resulting from the use of this drug.

Figure 2 Gene mutations identified by DNA sequence analysis of human breast tumors are used in multidimensional functional analysis to develop new clinical therapeutic targets. [Edith Sanford Breast Cancer Institute]

As such, the Avastin story is a cautionary tale that “the best laid plans of mice and men” can go awry despite strong evidence of supporting theory and early stage clinical trial validation. Moreover, statistical analyses suggest that approximately 70% of phase III clinical trials of drugs that looked promising in pre-clinical and phase I-II studies do not show a significant clinical benefit at the end of the clinical testing program, at a cost of billions of dollars, many research years and thousands of cancer patients who do not benefit medically from enrollment in these clinical trials [1].

The moral of this story has not gone unnoticed. To avoid traveling such a long clinical distance without therapeutic guideposts, some researchers are designing new clinical trial protocols in the hope of avoiding these costly detours in the future. Given the enormous cost and lengthy duration of conventional stage III trials, these clinicians have begun to re-think methodology and protocols used in the gold-standard large scale randomized clinical trials to fine tune and pinpoint potential data trends

earlier on in the drug testing cycle. The newer paradigm emerging from this re-assessment involves abandoning the notion of homogeneous patient populations within clearly defined clinical categories to an emphasis on small scale individualized studies of patients with carefully drawn genomic profiles to assess the clinical benefit of therapeutic approaches targeted to the individual patient’s cancer.

The rationale for this paradigm shift is provided by increasing evidence garnered from extensive cancer genome databases suggesting that cancers with similar histological and pathological parameters may represent a form of convergent evolution resulting from many different combinations of genetic mutations that can be mapped and used to design personalized therapeutic protocols. Such an approach to cancer treatment of necessity requires a different type of clinical trial. It has been estimated that there are more than 800 gene targeted therapeutics currently in development and the sheer enormity of the pipeline flow would result in inestimable clinical trial costs as well as wasting valuable research time better directed toward providing these specialized drugs to patients whose genetic profiles suggest that they might receive a positive clinical benefit.

Prominent among these newer paradigmatic approaches is I-SPY 2, a novel clinical approach that uses an adaptive research protocol based on Bayesian statistics. I-SPY 2 is sponsored by the Biomarker Consortium and the National Institutes of Health (NIH) and has been focused since 2010 specifically on assessing therapeutic outcome for women with high-risk aggressive breast cancer. A total of 10 gene biomarkers and 12 gene-targeted therapeutics are currently being testing in small scale trials with ongoing feedback [1] (see Figure 3).

Contribution of known genes to familial aggregation of breast cancer

Figure 3 Genes implicated in familial breast cancers (#www.mayo.edu)

Will this approach provide a more predictive empirical platform for assessing clinical efficacy? Perhaps, if there is no interference from the complex and unpredictable results set in motion by small

genetic changes as suggested by Chaos Theory. Unfortunately, the rolling of the genetic dice may not comprise the sole variable that determines cancer risk and disease progression. While it is clear that genetic mutations play an important causal role in the process of malignant transformation, the complex biological evolution of an incipient lesion to aggressive metastatic disease involves many local and systemic factors that may be equally important in defining the cancer phenotype.

Moreover, physiological studies suggest that genetic mutation may not be the sole determinant of cancer progression, a process that may be affected significantly by immune system dysfunction, particularly the activation of pro-inflammatory pathways. Even the process of metastasis itself, the hallmark of lethal cancer progression, does not appear to be the direct result of primary genetic mutations, but rather the end result of complex intersecting “chaotic” pathways that may result in the progression of a localized tumor to systemic disease. In addition, important research studies have implicated surrounding stromal tissues of the tumor microenvironment as pivotal players in tumor progression and systemic disease. The notion that targeting one or several genes implicated in early stage cancer causation may disrupt or delay later stages of cancer progression may be an overly simplistic rationale for the use of gene targeted approaches in many cancers of complex genotype and phenotype (see Figure 4)[2].

Figure 4 Representation of a functional genomic network in breast cancer [2]

So what should we do? Perhaps the conception of personalized medicines in cancer treatment should be expanded beyond the classification of cancer causing genes as the primary diagnostic determinant for therapeutic application, to a broader multi-faceted approach that takes into account the critical aetiological parameters that distinguish the major groups of human cancers. Distinctive therapeutic approaches may be required due to fundamental biological differences between sporadic and inherited cancers, hematological

cancers versus solid tumor malignancies and pediatric cancers versus the more common adult onset carcinomas. For example, cancers resulting from inherited genetic predispositions, such as *BRCA-1* breast cancer, *apc* associated familial colon cancer and others may be more amenable to specific genotargeted approaches than non-inherited “sporadic” cancers that originate from multiple and diverse genetic lesions, a category that includes most adult-onset cancers. Likewise, leukemias/lymphomas resulting from specific translocations, inversions or other genetic lesions that are an aberrant by-product of hematopoietic differentiation may profit from genetic screening and targeted therapeutic applications, as illustrated by the success of Gleevec for CML and Rituxumab (Rituxan), a monoclonal antibody that specifically targets CD20+leukemias/lymphomas. Yet another aetiological category encompasses Childhood malignancies resulting from dysregulated embryonic genes that may be amenable to a gene-targeted approach. Determining how the roll of the genetic dice produces a specific malignancy may be a critical tool in designing individualized therapies that target these causal genetic errors.

In contrast, many common adult carcinomas may evolve over a long period of time, emerging from a dysregulated genetic background that ultimately alters local and systemic parameters responsible for malignant progression. Cancers of this type may require multi-faceted systemic therapeutic approaches that target broad-spectrum parameters of disease progression. Clinical evidence of the therapeutic effect of aspirin on colon cancer development and recurrence is a proof of principle supporting this approach. Though we may not fully understand the complex processes that underscore the biological evolution of many complex adult-onset malignancies or control the roll of the genetic dice responsible for setting this process in motion, we can set our therapeutic sites on a larger playing field that limits the consequences of genetic lesions to intercept or even reverse the systemic outcome of progressive disease.

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